

Analysis of Risk Factors of Stillbirths using Recode Classification at a Tertiary Care Centre in Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract:

Stillbirths are a cause for concern globally. Stillbirth rate is a key indicator of quality of care given during antenatal and intranatal period. High prevalence of stillbirths in India necessitates analysis of risk factors of stillbirths both at national and local level.

Aim: To determine the maternal and fetal factors causing stillbirths.

Methods: The present study was conducted in the department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam. It was a hospital based observational study for a period of one year from January 2023 to December 2023. Case sheets were analysed for risk factors of stillbirths. Results tabulated and analysed using Microsoft excel.

Results: A total of 5,912 births occurred during the period of one year and 146 were stillbirths. The still birth rate was 24.69 per 1000 births. The maximum number of still births occurred in the age group below 20 years (54.1%). Multigravida had increased risk of stillbirths with 87 cases (59.58%). Still births were maximum in low socioeconomic status (56.16%). Stillbirths were highest in gestational age 28-32 weeks and was 58(39.72%). The maximum number of cases seen in the birth weight category above 2000-3000 grams, 68 cases (46.57%).

Conclusions: The corner stone of preventing stillbirths is good antenatal care. Prevention of anemia by iron folic acid supplementation, early identification of hypertension in pregnancy and its appropriate management is essential.

Keywords: Stillbirth, Recode Classification, Causes Of Stillbirth, Perinatal Audit.

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Introduction

Stillbirth is one of the serious maternal and child health problems across the globe. Stillbirth rate (SBR) is defined as the number of babies born with no sign of life at 28 weeks or more of gestation, per 1000 total births. Globally 13.9 stillbirths per 1000 births have been reported in 2019 [1,2]

More than one third of these stillbirths were concentrated in India (17.3% with SBR 13.9) along with Pakistan (9.7%) and Nigeria (8.7%)² Pregnancy complications, including anaemia, eclampsia and other hypertensive

disorders, antepartum and intrapartum haemorrhage, abnormal fetal position, breech presentation and obstructed labour significantly increase the odds of stillbirth. [3] However, in response to the global Every New-born Action Plan (ENAP) launched at the World Health Assembly (2014) to attain 'Single Digit Neonatal Mortality Rate (NMR) by 2030' and 'Single Digit SBR by 2030', Indian government developed New-born Action Plan (INAP) for the country. [4]

The definition of a stillbirth varies across countries. The American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists define fetal demise as the death of a fetus past 20 weeks of gestation and or weight of 500 grams and above. [5] In United Kingdom, stillbirth is defined as delivery of a baby with no signs of life after 24 weeks of Pregnancy. [6] However for the purpose of statistics for international comparison, as per World Health Organization (WHO), stillbirth (SB) is the birth of a newborn after 28th completed week and weighing 1000gms or more when the baby does not breathe or show any sign of life after delivery, before onset of labor (ante partum death) or during labor (intra partum death). [7] Stillbirth is a significant contributor to perinatal mortality in developing countries and it is a devastating experience for parents as well as obstetricians.

Aim of the Study: To determine the maternal and fetal factors causing stillbirths.

Material and Methods

The present study was conducted in the department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam. It was a hospital based retrospective observational study for a period of one year from January 2023 to December 2023. Case sheets were analysed for risk factors of stillbirths. The still births were analysed using Re Co De (relevant condition at death) classification. Demographic data and investigations were collected. Mode of delivery, birth weight and gestational age was recorded and analysed. Results tabulated and analysed using Microsoft excel.

Inclusion Criteria: Stillbirths of more than 28 weeks or ≥ 1000 gm of weight.

Exclusion Criteria: Abortions and stillbirths of less than 28 weeks/ less than 1000 grams

Indicator Definition and Calculation: The indicator is calculated as the number of stillbirths per 1000 births (live and stillbirths) during a specified time period.

Numerator

Number of fetuses born per year with no sign of life and born with birthweight of ≥ 1000 g, or ≥ 28 weeks' gestation, or ≥ 35 cm body length during a specified time period.

Denominator: Total number of births (per 1000) in a specified time period.

To compute the rate per 1000 births, the numerator is divided by the denominator and multiplied by 1000. The denominator should include both live and stillbirths, including babies born live and who have later died (i.e. neonatal death). The definition of stillbirth may vary depending on definitions within the health facility and/or national or sub national vital statistics offices. To align with the global indicator, a stillbirth (or fetal death) is defined as a baby born with no signs of life after a given threshold. For international comparison, WHO defines stillbirth as birth weight of ≥ 1000 g; if the birth weight is not available, a gestational age of ≥ 28 weeks or a length of ≥ 35 cm (ICD-10) is used.

Results

A total of 5,912 births occurred during the period of one year and 146 were stillbirths. The still birth rate was 24.69 per 1000 births

Table 1 Demographic Characteristics

Demographic Characteristics	Number of stillbirth (n=146)	Percentage (%)
Age		
< 20 years	79	54.1%
20-30 years	54	36.98%
>30 years	13	8.9%
Parity		
Primi	59	40.41%
Multi	87	59.58%
Ses		
Low	82	56.16%
Middle	36	24.65%
High	28	19.17%

The maximum number of still births occurred in the age group below 20 years (54.1%) and 54 cases (36.98%) in the age group 20-30 years. The number of cases in the age group above 30 years was 13(8.9%).Multigravida had increased risk of

stillbirths with 87 cases (59.58%) and primi had 59 cases(40.41%). Still births were maximum in low socioeconomic status (56.16%)and lowest in high economic status(19.17%).

Table 2: Gestational Age

Gestational age (in weeks)	Stillbirths (n=146)	Percentage (%)
28-32 weeks	58	39.72%
32-36 weeks	46	31.50%
36 -38 weeks	31	21.23%
>38 weeks	11	7.53%
Total	146	

The number of stillbirths in the gestational age 28-32 weeks was 58(39.72%),gestational age 32-36 weeks was 46(31.50%),gestational age 36-38 weeks was 31(21.23%), gestational a >38 weeks was 11(7.53%).

Chart 1: Gestational Age

Table 3: Mode of Delivery

Mode of delivery	Stillbirths (n =146)	Percentage (%)
Vaginal Delivery	103	70.54%
LSCS	43	29.45%
Total	146	

The maximum number of stillbirths occurred in the vaginal delivery group and was 103 cases (70.54%) and 29.45% in the LSCS group

Chart 2: Mode of delivery

Table 4: Birth Weight

Birth Weight(grams)	Stillbirths (n=146)	Percentage (%)
1000-2000 gms	36	24.65%
2000-3000 gms	68	46.57%
Above 3000 gms	42	28.76%
Total	146	

The maximum number of cases seen in the birth weight category above 2000-3000 grams, 68 cases (46.57%) followed by 42 cases (28.76%) in the above 3000 grams group.

Chart 3: Birth Weight

Table 5: Stillbirths according to relevant condition at death (ReCoDe classification)

Relevant condition at death	Details	Stillbirths	Percentage (%)
Group A Fetus	Lethal congenital anomaly	6	4.10%
	Twin to twin transfusion	3	2.05%
	Fetal growth restriction	4	2.73%
Group B Umbilical cord	Cord prolapse	6	4.10%
Group C Placental	Placental abruption	24	16.43%
	Placenta previa	2	1.36%
	Past dates	4	2.73%
Group D Amniotic fluid	Oligo hydramnios	11	7.53%
Group E Uterus	Rupture uterus	5	3.42%
Group F Mother	Diabetes	7	4.79%
	Hypertension	38	26.02%
	Anemia	10	6.84%
	Hypothyroidism	2	1.36%
	Fever	8	5.47%
	Jaundice	1	0.68%
Group G Intrapartum	Asphyxia	3	2.05%
Group H Trauma	Nil	0	0%
Group I Unclassified	Unidentified	12	8.21%
Total		146	

Lethal congenital anomalies was seen in 6 cases (4.10%), twin to twin transfusion in 3 cases (2.05%), fetal growth restriction in 4 cases (2.73%). Cord prolapse was seen in 4.10%. Placental abruption was seen in 16.43%, placenta previa in 1.36%, and past dates in 2.73%. Oligo hydramnios was seen in 7.53%. Rupture of the uterus was seen in 3.42%.

Diabetes was seen in 4.79%, hypertension in 26.02%, anemia in 6.84% and fever was seen in 5.47%. Intrapartum asphyxia was seen in 2.05%.

Discussion

Mustafa MA et al [8] has reported that stillbirth were common (73.7%) in age group of 20-35 years. Njoku CO et al [9] stated that stillbirth is common (33.7%) in age group of 30-34 years. Showghy et al [10] stated that pregnancy at the age of 16 years and less than 16 years increase the risk of stillbirths by 4 times. Fretts RC et al [11] has concluded that age of 35 and more can increase risk of foetus death by 1.5 times. In the present study, the maximum number of still births occurred in the age group below 20 years (54.1%) and 54 cases

(36.98%) in the age group 20-30 years. The number of cases in the age group above 30 years was 13(8.9%) similar to the study by Showghy et al. Teenage pregnancy seems to increase risk of stillbirth.

In the present study, multi gravida had increased risk of stillbirths with 87 cases (59.58%) similar to Njoku C.O et al who stated that proportion of stillbirths was higher in multigravida (82.1%) whereas Mustufa MA et al concluded that proportion of stillbirths was higher in primigravida patient (61%).

Mustufa MA et al concluded that proportion of stillbirth was higher (55.47%) between 32-37 weeks of gestational age. In the present study maximum stillbirths occurred in the gestational age group 36-38 weeks and was 58(39.72%).

A meta-analysis by Mondal D et al [12] which includes data on more than 30 million births, links sex with stillbirth, the risk being about 10% higher in male fetuses. The reason for male preponderance is unclear but may be linked to the difference in male and female development. Male embryos have faster development and higher metabolic rates than female embryos and this potentially leave male fetuses more vulnerable to distress or death from a range of stressors including endocrine fluctuation, oxidative stress and faster nutritional depletion when they encountered stressful conditions.

The ReCoDe system of classification helped us to identify a cause in 80.8% of stillbirths. In present study, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy was cause of stillbirths in 27(24.8%). Njoku C.O et al reported 18.9% of stillbirths due to hypertensive disorders. Sharma S et al.[13] concluded that PIH accounted for 19.6% of stillbirths. In PIH, vasospasm decreases blood flow to all organs, particularly uteroplacental perfusion. So oxygen supply to fetus decreases and leads to fetal hypoxia and stillbirth.

In present study, stillbirth occurred due to anemia in 10 cases (6.84%) compared to 12.2% reported by Njoku C.O et al. Iron deficiency is the cause of anaemia in pregnancy and iron a supplementation is recommended. In present study placental abruption and placenta previa as a placental cause for stillbirths was seen in 16.43% and in 1.36% respectively. Njoku C.O et al reported that abruptio placenta and placenta previa accounted for 9.3% and 2.2% cases of stillbirth. Sharma S et al [13] reported antepartum haemorrhage in 12% as a cause of stillbirth. Antepartum haemorrhage leads to maternal blood loss leading to hypovolemic anaemia, hypoxia, hypertonic uterine contraction causes fetal hypoxia and death.

Lethal congenital anomalies was seen in 6 cases (4.10%), twin to twin transfusion in 3 cases

(2.05%), fetal growth restriction in 4 cases (2.73%). Cord prolapse was seen in 4.10%. Diabetes was seen in 4.79%, hypertension in 26.02%, anemia in 6.84% and fever was seen in 5.47%. Intrapartum asphyxia was seen in in 2.05%.

In the present study lethal congenital anomalies was seen in 6 cases (4.10%), twin to twin transfusion in 3 cases (2.05%), fetal growth restriction in 4 cases (2.73%). Cord prolapse was seen in 4.10%, Njoku C.O et al reported stillbirth due to congenital malformation in 1% while Sharma S et al [13] reported stillbirth due to congenital malformation in 8%.

In present study, the maximum number of stillbirths occurred in the vaginal delivery group and was 103 cases (70.54%) and 29.45% in the LSCS group Njoku C.O et al reported that normal vaginal delivery occurred in 74.3% patients of stillbirth while operative procedure was needed in 25.7%. In present study, unexplained stillbirth occurred in 8.2% whereas in the study by Njoku C.O et al it was 20.8%.

Conclusion

The corner stone of preventing stillbirths is good antenatal care. Prevention of anemia by iron folic acid supplementation, early identification of hypertension in pregnancy and its appropriate management is essential.

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